

IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF STUDENTS THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL FACILITATION

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Introduction: As the educational landscape continues to shape, technology will play an important role in revolutionizing how independent learning is organized and facilitated. The practice of using technologies for the development of pedagogical interest, education and training offers new ways to improve independent learning. In this article, we explore how technology can empower learners and facilitate continuous improvement in independent learning environments.

1. Convenience and flexibility: Technology has broken down barriers to access, making education available to learners regardless of time, place or socioeconomic background. Online learning platforms, digital libraries, and interactive learning resources provide learners with endless opportunities for self-directed learning and exploration, tailored to their unique needs and interests. allows for adaptation of training experiences.

2. Personalized learning: Technology enables personalized learning paths, meeting individual learning styles and preferences. Intelligent learning systems, adaptive learning platforms and data analytics enable learners to receive personalized feedback, recommendations and content based on their strengths, weaknesses and achievements. This personalized approach empowers learners to improve at their own pace, enhancing understanding and retention.

3. Collaborative Learning: Technology facilitates collaboration and knowledge sharing among independent learners. Online communities, discussion forums, and virtual classrooms allow learners to connect with peers, mentors, and experts, creating a collaborative learning environment. Through active participation and collaboration, learners can broaden their perspectives, refine their ideas, and contribute to the continuous improvement of their learning journey together.

4. Gaming and interactive learning: Gaming techniques and interactive learning platforms engage learners through interactive simulations, quizzes and challenges. By adding elements of competition, reward, and progress, technology

motivates learners to actively participate and continuously improve. A game environment taps into intrinsic motivation, sparks learner interest, and encourages a growth mindset.

5. Data-driven decision making. One of the biggest advantages of technology in independent learning is the abundance of data that can be collected, analyzed and used for continuous improvement. Teachers can track learner progress, identify areas for improvement, and make data-driven decisions to optimize learning experiences. This data-driven approach enables educators to adapt and refine instructional methods to meet the needs of individual learners, leading to continuous improvement and better learning outcomes.

Further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 is determined due to the achievements in the Strategy of Actions on raising a highly educated and competent generation in higher education institutions, creating a reserve of qualified scientific and pedagogical personnel. In the educational system of developed countries, at the same time, many reforms implemented in our country, in the development of civil society based on democratic principles, the need to further improve the professional skills of teachers and the technology of organizing independent education of students in the higher education system, to improve the quality of professional training of students emphasized improvement. Facilitation is the pedagogical culture of the future teacher. The phenomenon of facilitation encompasses both group dynamics (influencing power) and individual dynamics. Facilitation (from English. Facilitate - to help, guide, facilitate) is one of the effective psychological, strategic tools and methods in its arsenal (master room) that help a person or team find the best solution to achieve results. using non-directional guidance and assistance technology. Today, it is generally recognized that the science of pedagogy is undergoing a transitional phase associated with updating the content and forms of the educational process. Famous psychologist A.G. Asmolov called this stage "an open road, from a useful culture to a culture of dignity." Therefore, a cultured person is not only an educated person, but also deserves the respect of others and self-respect. Therefore, the problem of implementing interaction with others, establishing relationships with the world, people and oneself is one of the most important tasks of our time.

In the rapidly changing world and in the conditions of increasing information flows, basic science knowledge is a mandatory but insufficient goal of education. It is very important and more difficult to form the ability of

students to independently distinguish, analyze, structure and effectively use it so that students not only acquire a set of knowledge, skills and abilities, but also realize themselves to the maximum and participate usefully in society. . Education is the process of educating and training a person aimed at achieving educational levels (educational standards, qualifications) set by the state. Education is one of the most important sub-systems of the state social sphere, which provides a systematic process of acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities of a person for effective use in professional activities.

Summary:

Pedagogical interest through technology has opened up new dimensions in independent education, providing great opportunities for professional development. Technologies are capable of continuously enhancing the educational experience for learners and teachers by encouraging convenience, personalized learning, collaboration, play and data-driven decision making. Supporting these technological advances creates a culture of self-directed learning improvement where learners can achieve their educational goals in an ever-evolving digital age.

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